

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND INTERAGENCY COOPERATION IN COMBATING MARITIME TRAFFICKING OF PERSONS

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Policy Statement

This policy brief is based on the recognition that combating maritime trafficking in persons requires more than advanced technological solutions or isolated public security strategies. It requires the construction of interagency arrangements that articulate police, legal, logistical, customs, financial, and community capacities, while taking into account the complexity of criminal networks that operate in convergent ways in the maritime space (Andreas & Greenhill, 2010).

The arguments developed here are based on evidence from regional and international initiatives, such as Project Turquoise (INTERPOL) and JIATF-South, as well as bottom-up practices mapped in the Global South (Organization of American States [OAS], 2024). These examples indicate that artificial intelligence, when applied critically and contextually, has the potential to amplify the effectiveness of responses to human trafficking, but only if it is incorporated as an analytical support tool, rather than as a substitute for institutional or community capacities.

By emphasizing the role of customs authorities, the multi-scale integration of data, and the intersection of logistical, financial, and operational dimensions, this document argues that confronting maritime trafficking in persons requires a coordinated effort guided by dismantling criminal networks, not by intensifying surveillance of migrant populations. The contributions of the Global South, forged under conditions of historical inequality and resource scarcity, offer relevant lessons for rethinking governance models that often privilege the transfer of technological packages from the Global North without considering local adaptability (Taylor, 2023).

Background

Combating maritime trafficking in persons takes place in a deeply interconnected criminal context, in which illicit activities such as drug trafficking, arms trafficking, smuggling of goods, and money laundering operate in a convergent and interdependent manner (Andreas & Greenhill, 2010). Studies on organized crime in Latin America highlight that these networks exploit the same routes, logistical infrastructures, and financial circuits, which require interagency approaches that break with fragmented, sectoral responses. In this scenario, customs authorities play a central role, not only in the inspection of goods, but in the detection of suspicious

patterns in cargo, routes, and documentation, in addition to accessing international bodies such as the World Customs Organization, and strengthening intelligence exchange (Joint Interagency Task Force South [JIATF-South], n.d.; INTERPOL, n.d.).

Initiatives such as Project Turquoise, coordinated by INTERPOL and UNODC, demonstrate how regional operations that bring together police, prosecutors, customs, and coast guards can yield significant gains in dismantling transnational networks by combining technical training, criminological analysis, and victim protection protocols (INTERPOL, n.d.). Similarly, the JIATF-South model exemplifies how integrating different spheres of government and intelligence-sharing can increase the effectiveness of actions against organized crime at sea, going beyond isolated confrontations with drugs or migrants (JIATF-South, n.d.).

However, both the European literature and critical analyses in the field of migration geopolitics warn of the risks of uncritically importing models from the Global North (Taylor, 2023). The externalization of security policies, often based on technological packages, tends to reinforce securitization logics that fall on migratory flows and not on criminal networks per se. In addition, these technology transfers can create institutional dependence and reduce countries in the Global South's autonomy, limiting their ability to develop solutions tailored to their social, cultural, and economic contexts (Taylor, 2023).

In contrast, bottom-up practices developed in Latin American and Caribbean countries have shown that local networks, coastal communities, and national agencies can build hybrid, innovative responses. These responses articulate community reporting, field monitoring, and flexible interagency coordination, often operating with limited resources but achieving significant impact (Organization of American States [OAS], 2024). In this scenario, artificial intelligence emerges not as a substitute for local capabilities but as an analytical tool capable of identifying patterns of criminal convergence, interpreting complex data, and assisting in the formulation of more effective, context-sensitive interventions. The centrality of the Global South, therefore, should not be ignored or subordinated, but recognized as a strategic source of knowledge, institutional innovation, and adaptive practices.

The literature also highlights that, in addition to operational difficulties, legal challenges represent a significant obstacle to international cooperation. Differences in legal definitions, penalties, and procedural procedures create gaps that criminal

networks exploit, requiring sophisticated strategies for legal harmonization and coordination (Voicescu, 2024). Platforms such as INTERPOL, SELEC, the Prüm Treaty, and structures such as Eurojust offer ways to mitigate these problems, but their effectiveness depends on processes of rapid communication and institutional trust between States.

Findings

Evidence gathered in different regional contexts indicates that practical interagency cooperation is an indispensable element in confronting maritime trafficking in persons and, more broadly, transnational criminal networks. Igwe's (2023) study of the Seme-Badagry corridor on the Nigeria-Benin border shows that the mere presence of multiple agencies, such as federal police, customs, immigration, and armed forces, does not guarantee effectiveness. On the contrary, the absence of jurisdictional clarity, overlapping functions, and interinstitutional conflicts tend to create operational gaps, vulnerabilities, and even opportunities for corruption. However, when there is effective articulation, even if limited, significant gains are achieved, especially in crossing data, identifying illicit routes, and planning operations based on shared intelligence.

Latin American experiences reinforce this diagnosis. INTERPOL's Project Turquesa promotes joint operations between Caribbean and Latin American countries, bringing together police, customs, prosecutors, and coast guards to confront human trafficking and migrant smuggling.

These operations stand out not only for the volume of interceptions carried out, but for their ability to integrate criminological analysis, technical training, and humanitarian support protocols (INTERPOL, n.d.). JIATF-South, for its part, shows how multi-scale operations, which unite military and civilian forces in transnational collaboration, achieve significant results by combining actions at sea with logistical and financial investigations on land (JIATF-South, n.d.). In the Brazilian context, studies show that customs have an underexplored role in interagency integration, despite having relevant strategic potential in alignment with international standards (Medeiros et al., 2025).

Studies in the European context offer an additional critical lens. Research highlights that, even with advanced regulatory frameworks, interagency cooperation is often lost in institutional fragmentation and excessive focus on border control, to the detriment of dismantling economic and logistical networks.

In addition, analyses of the geopolitics of anti-smuggling policies, as in the Canadian case, warn of the risk that the transfer of capabilities and technologies to countries in the Global South will result in dependence on and reproduction of decontextualized securitization logics (Taylor, 2023).

A concrete example is the joint operation carried out between Romania and the United Kingdom, in which a Joint Investigation Team allowed the identification, arrest, and prosecution of members of a transnational sex trafficking network, as well as the release and support of victims (Voicescu, 2024). Integration among prosecutors, police, and experts from both countries was key to collecting and analyzing evidence in real time, conducting interrogations via videoconference, and coordinating searches, illustrating the transformative potential of JITs when well implemented.

The literature on convergence crime helps to understand why sectoral responses fail. Networks involved in maritime trafficking in persons often operate simultaneously in the trafficking of drugs, weapons, and illicit financial assets, which requires approaches that transcend isolated criminal categories (Andreas & Greenhill, 2010). In this sense, artificial intelligence offers a differentiated potential: instead of reinforcing population surveillance practices, it can be applied to identify hidden patterns of criminal convergence, cross-referencing logistical, legal, and financial information, and supporting strategic decisions aimed at dismantling organizations.

Finally, bottom-up practices in the Global South show that effectiveness does not depend exclusively on technological investments, but on institution-building processes that value local capacities, community articulation, and adaptive innovation. These practices constitute a strategic field for the ethical and effective use of AI, which can learn from local models, distinguish them from imported standards, and calibrate interventions aligned with regional specificities (OAS, 2024).

This strategic field can be expanded by institutionalizing local insights into AI design. Rather than automating surveillance or replicating Global North systems, bottom-up approaches to artificial intelligence should be explored. These approaches are grounded in participatory design involving customs agents, port workers, and coastal communities, the use of localized datasets that reflect regional trafficking methods and forged documentation, and the establishment of feedback loops that allow human users to refine and guide AI predictions over time. Transparency can be strengthened through open-source collaborations with regional universities or NGOs, transforming AI from a tool of control into one of co-creation.

The importance of such collaborative frameworks is reinforced by recent operations such as the July 2025 Europol-led initiative across 44 countries, which resulted in the arrest of 158 traffickers and the safeguarding of nearly 1,200 victims. This example underscores the value of integrating international databases and coordination platforms with contextual intelligence and bottom-up contributions to achieve strategic impact.

Recommendations

In light of the evidence analyzed, it is recommended that policies to combat maritime trafficking in persons prioritize intelligence-driven, context-sensitive, and human rights interagency strategies. First, it is essential to consolidate cooperation mechanisms between police, public prosecutors, coast guards, customs authorities, and civil society organizations, ensuring continuous flows of information and joint operation protocols (INTERPOL, n.d.-b; JIATF-South, n.d.). This integration must transcend isolated criminal categories and contemplate the logic of convergence crime to confront transnational networks that operate simultaneously in human trafficking, drug trafficking, arms smuggling, and asset laundering (Andreas & Greenhill, 2010).

Second, it is essential to incorporate artificial intelligence technologies as analytical support tools, rather than as substitutes for local institutional capacities. AI should be used to distinguish logistical, financial, and operational patterns that characterize criminal convergence, helping to identify networks, map flows, and guide strategic decisions. However, its use must be anchored in robust ethical safeguards, with attention to mitigating algorithmic biases, protecting personal data, and qualified human oversight (Taylor, 2023).

Third, it is recommended to strengthen bottom-up practices in the Global South, supporting the co-construction of technological solutions adjusted to local realities. Instead of uncritically exporting models from the Global North, international cooperation policies should invest in horizontal partnerships, fostering institutional and community innovation, promoting technological autonomy, and ensuring that countries in the Global South are not only receivers but also producers and co-creators of solutions (OAS, 2024).

It is recommended to invest in the creation and strengthening of Joint Investigation Teams (JITs), which will make it possible to overcome the bureaucratic obstacles of mutual legal assistance and to speed up the circulation of information between States. In addition, the importance of training programs for local police officers is highlighted, enabling officers to recognize hidden signs of victimization, especially when they involve vulnerable foreign populations (Voicescu, 2024). Artificial intelligence can serve as an ally in integrating operational, legal, and financial data, further strengthening these integrated strategies. It is also crucial to strengthen information flows and operational protocols among customs authorities, police, coast guards, and public prosecutors, aligning local practices with international benchmarks (Medeiros et al., 2025) to expand the financial and logistical tracking capacity of criminal networks.

Finally, it is suggested to expand investments in technical and legal training, considering the complexity of operations at sea, where the role of customs authorities is particularly relevant. The formation of mixed teams specialized in financial, logistical, and digital crime, as proposed in Project CCISOM, can expand the capacity to track criminal networks in their multiple dimensions and ensure more effective responses that are less focused on migratory securitization (INTERPOL, n.d.-a).

Final Considerations

Confronting maritime trafficking in persons and associated criminal networks depends on the articulation between institutional capacities, local knowledge, and judicious use of technologies such as artificial intelligence. The evidence analyzed shows that interagency cooperation should be understood not only as formal integration between agencies but also as the practical construction of information flows, joint methodologies, and coordination mechanisms to address the complexity of operations at sea, including logistical, financial, and legal aspects.

The experience accumulated in countries of the Global South reveals that adaptive approaches, built from local practices and community articulation, achieve relevant results even in contexts of resource scarcity. This learning should not be marginalized in international projects that seek to incorporate AI or other technological innovations. On the contrary, algorithms and intelligent systems will only be practical if they are calibrated with contextual data, taking into account regional patterns and institutional specificities, and if they are designed with the active participation of local actors.

The mere transfer of models from the Global North tends to generate significant side effects, such as the reinforcement of strategies focused on migration control, the diversion of focus from criminal structures, and the expansion of technological dependencies. A more robust path involves investing in joint work platforms, valuing bottom-up practices, and building intelligence systems that respond to the real needs of maritime operations, while prioritizing dismantling networks and protecting victims without widening institutional inequalities.

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